

Implications of Wastage of Human Resources in Secondary Schools in Meme Division

Lontchi Madeleine

M.Ed, PhD (in view) University of Buea, South West Region, Cameroon

ABSTRACT

This study titled “Implications of Wastage of Human Resources in Secondary Schools in Meme Division” is based on the problem of educational wastage in school establishments. The general objective was to establish the relation between school human resources and wastage in secondary schools in Meme Division of the South west Region of Cameroon. One research question was posed to examine the issue under investigation.

Being a quantitative study, the survey research design was used. The target population constituted 362 secondary school principals in the South west Region of Cameroon. A questionnaire on educational infrastructural inputs was used to collect data, and data obtained was analyzed using frequencies, percentages, means and standard deviation. The Chi – square test was used to test hypotheses at 0.5level of significance

The Item intended to verify the relationship between qualified teachers and wastage.

Analyses revealed that 5 schools always have qualified teachers, 23 schools sometimes have qualified teachers. It was also found that there is positive relationship between qualified teachers and wastage. As confirm by the result of hypothesis testing. Analyses shows that χ^2 calculated (16.08) > χ^2 calculated value (7.93). This means that when a school has qualified teachers, educational wastage can be reduce. When there is lack of qualified teachers, the rate of school repetition increases. This result agrees with the result of research Magnet (2007) that hold that student with certified teachers perform better than student with teachers who have no certification

or emergency certificate. He also alerted that teachers, who have professional education training or pedagogy, produce higher student’s achievement than those who enter the profession and lack this background.

Item intended to verify the relationship between quantity and teachers at all the subjects and school repetition. Analyses revealed that 7 schools always have adequate quantity of teachers in all the subjects 21 schools, sometimes have adequate quality in all the subjects and 40 schools often have adequate quantity of teachers in all the subjects. It was also found that there is a positive relationship between enough quantity of teachers in all subjects and school repetition. As confirm by the result of table above shows that χ^2 calculated (13.69) > χ^2 critical value (7.92). This means that quantity of teachers in the entire subject can reduce the rate of repetition.

Item intended to verify the relationship between teachers with experience and school repetition. Analyses revealed that 9 schools always have teachers with experience, 20 schools sometimes have teachers with experience, 36 schools often have teachers with experience. It was also found that there is positive relationship between teachers experience and school repetition. As confined by the result above .It shows that χ^2 calculated (10.18)> χ^2 critical (7.92) value. This means that schools which have teachers with experience can have low rate of repetition, while schools which have teachers without experience can have high rate of school repetition. This result agree with magnet (2007) finding, who hold that there is a negative effect when a high proportion of inexperienced teachers are present in school, in terms

of higher dropout rate and lower students achievement scores.

Item intended to verify the relationship between support staff for discipline and school repetition.

Analyses shows that, 10 schools always have support staff for discipline, 15 schools sometimes have support staff for discipline, 40 schools often have support staff for discipline. It was found that there is a positive relationship between availability of support staff for discipline and school repetition. As confirmed by the result of table above. It reveals that X^2 calculated (11.27) $> X^2$ critical value (7.92).

This means that the availability of support staff for discipline can reduce the rate of school repetition.

Item intended to verify the relationship between availability of guidance and counseling and school repetition. Table above reveals that 71 schools often have staff for guidance and counseling. It was also found that there is no positive relationship between availability of staff for guidance and counseling and school repetition. As confined by the result of table 71. It shows X^2 calculated (0.042) $< X^2$ critical value (7.92) this mean that the availability of staff for guidance and counseling does not influence the rate of repetition in school.

Results from this study and those of other researches show that when human resources of standards are available in school, there will be low rate of educational wastage. On the other hand, if these resources are neglected or left out completely, there will be high rate of school wastages. It also reveals that human is still lacking in a higher percentage in schools.

Keyword: Human Resources, Wastage

INTRODUCTION

Human resource constitutes a vital vein of any institution. The human resource in the school system includes teachers, support staff in the school, students, parents, community members and a host of other interest and social groups. Human resources is responsible for planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling, manipulating and maintaining other forms of resources, its administrative and forecasting ability placed it ahead of other forms of resources. The availability of human resources is not only required in school administration, but their quality and quantity

must be considered if effective and efficient teaching and learning is to be guaranteed. According to Likert (1969) all activities of any institution are initiated by the persons that make up that institution. Plant, offices, computer, automated equipments and all inputs that an institution uses are unproductive except for human effort and direction.

The problem of educational wastage at the secondary school level of education, which manifests in high rate of failure in public examinations, is a great concern to every stakeholder in education. Wastage, which is an indication of internal inefficiency, is recorded when an investment does not yield the desired gain or product, or when investment produces result that is considered to be lower than the targeted value (Adesina, 1983). While tracing the history of Nigerian educational development since 1960, Adesina (1983) and Durosaro (1985) identified wastage as one of the impediments to its growth. The authors also identified elements of wastage as dropouts (results of illness, poor academic performance, dismissals, inadequacies on the part of parents), repetition (where government had to pay twice instead of once) and failure at the end of the course. A system is said to be externally inefficient if the graduate turned out is not what the society, economy or higher level of education wants. The expectation is that certificated school leavers from secondary schools would gain admission into higher level of education or become productive workers and good citizens who would be able to contribute to the development of their society and make the nation truly self-reliant. But, the reality is that many of these school leavers have to sit for examinations again and again for them to have the minimum requirements to proceed to the next educational level. With this repetition, many of them waste precious years for failing to pass at one sitting. Longe and Durosaro (1988) described internal efficiency as the extent of the ability of educational systems to minimize costs and reduce wastage resulting from repetitions, dropouts and failures. The authors stated that an internally efficient educational system is one which turns out graduates without wasting any student year. The indicators of internal efficiency are wastage rate and graduation rate. As Abdulkareem, Fasasi and Akinnubi (2011) noted, the question of internal efficiency is ultimately linked to the issue of resource allocation and utilization. Resources are very important in the development of qualitative education. The success or the failure of any system of education

depends on the quality and quantity of human resources made available to it and the use to which such resources are put (Adeogun, 1989). All educational resources are vital to the achievement of national objectives. Human resources, especially the teaching staff, are to control other resources and ensure that national goals and objectives are achieved. No matter how beautiful the programmes and assets of an institution are, without the teaching staff, attainment of the institutional goals and objectives would prove abortive. For instance, overstaffing or an unhealthy shortage could usher in negative effects on the school internal efficiency. The number of times a resource can be used in a week compared with the number of times it could be in use is referred to as the 'use or 'utilization factor' and it is expressed as a percentage. High use factors represent maximum use of resources while low use factors reflect the opposite. On the other hand, resource utilization, according to Okunola (1985), is defined as the quantity of resource provided for use in secondary schools. From this operational definition, educational resources are over-utilized when they are in short supply; this has a negative effect on teaching-learning situations. When there is under-staffing for instance, teacher-student ratio is higher than the standard and teaching-learning efficiency and effectiveness become greatly reduced. Under-utilization of resources is also manifested in several ways - when laboratories play ground, student chairs and tables, and other physical and material resources are not in regular use or when secondary school teachers have an average of 20 teaching periods per week as opposed to a norm of 25 and 30 periods. Ojuawo (1989) showed that a positive significant relationship exists between variables such as class size and teacher-pupil ratio and performance in examinations. Performance in schools is related to size and qualification of teachers as well as teaching quality, which is an indication that teachers are a key input in educational production. Thus, an adequate supply of skilled teachers should be a prominent policy concern of any nation.

Statement of the Research Problem

Strategic human resource management improves the performance of institutions and firms (Beer et al., 1985). This approach emphasizes the importance of congruence between human resource activities and organizational objectives. Recent research has focused on the links between human resource management and performance (Guest 2003; 2004; Purcell 2002; 2004), and much of the growing body of international

literature in the field is built upon the premise that human resource management is linked closely to the emergent strategies, especially of large organizations, both public and private organizations. To provide efficient education and training services, the capacities and skills of staff in the various offices and organizations involved should be commensurate with the tasks they perform (MOEST 2005). Currently, in majority of cases there are gaps between competencies and the responsibilities of those mandated to undertake provision and management of education. The various ministries of Education in Cameroon a charged are with the responsibility of training and in servicing education managers to enable them manage education services and institutions effectively. On the other hand, the school managers who have been trained in Human Resource Management may or may not be adopting the HRM practices in their schools. Either way, secondary schools need to embrace human resource management practices that will help cope with wastages facing their work force and ensure continued education excellence in Cameroon.

If education must become sustainable, then the management of human resources must be closely monitored. Also, there is an incumbent need of constantly upgrading human resources so as to guarantee consistency and efficiency. It is based on this premise that this study sought to examine the wastages of human resources in secondary schools within the Meme Division of the South West Region of Cameroon.

Objective of the Study

The paramount objective of this study is to examine the relationship between human resources and wastage in secondary schools in Meme division, south-west region of Cameroon.

Research Question

What is the relationship between human resources and wastage in secondary schools in meme division, south-west region of Cameroon?

Hypotheses

Ho: There is no significant relationship between human resources and wastages in secondary schools in the Meme Division of the South West Region of Cameroon

Ha: There is a significant relationship between human resources and wastages in secondary schools in the

Meme Division of the South West Region of Cameroon

CONCEPTUAL BACKGROUND

Human resource constitutes a vital vein of any institution. The human resource in the school system includes teachers, support staff in the school, students, parents, community members and a host of other interest and social groups. Human resources is responsible for planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling, manipulating and maintaining other forms of resources, its administrative and forecasting ability placed it ahead of other forms of resources. The availability of human resources is not only required in school administration, but their quality and quantity must be considered if effective and efficient administration is to be guaranteed. According to Likert (1969) all activities of any institution are initiated by the persons that make up that institution. Plant, offices, computer, automated equipments and all inputs that an institution uses are unproductive except for human effort and direction.

Elwood and James (1996) observed that in governing human resources three major trends are typically considered, they include:

- A. Demographics: The characteristics of a population/ workforce for example age, gender or social class. The type of trend may have an effect in relation to pension offering, insurance packages etc.
- B. Divesirty: The variation within the population/ workplace changes in the society now mean that a larger proportion of organization is made up of “baby boomers or old workers in comparison to thirty years ago. Advocates of workplace divert advocates an employee base that is a minor reflection of the make- up of the society in so far as race, gender, sexual orientation etc.
- C. Skills and Qualification: As industries move from manual to more managerial profession, so does the need for more highly skilled graduates. If the market is tight (i.e. not enough staff for the job) employers must compete for employees by offering financial rewards, community investments etc. Every aspect of an institution’s activities is determined by the competence, motivation and general effectiveness of its human resource. It is noteworthy that the quality of human resources in any educational system

determines to a great extent the quality of the system itself and professional staff in particular are crucial to the formulation and successful implementation of the education policies and programmes in any country. (Nakpodia,2010). Relevance of Human Resources Management (HRM) in School Administration. A school cannot build a good team of working professionals without good Human Resources. The key functions of the Human Resources Management (HRM) team include recruiting people, training them, performance appraisals, motivating employees as well as workplace communication, workplace safety, and much more.

The beneficial effects of these functions are discussed thus: (i.) Recruitment and Training: This is one of the major responsibilities of the human resource management team. The HR managers come up with plans and strategies for hiring the right kind of people. They design the criteria which is best suited for a specific job description. Their other tasks related to recruitment include formulating the obligations of an employee and the scope of tasks assigned to him or her. Based on these two factors, the contract of an employee with the company is prepared. When needed, they also provide training to the employees according to the requirements of the organization. Thus, the staff members get the opportunity to sharpen their existing skills or develop specialized skills which in turn, will help them to take up some new roles. (ii.) Performance Appraisals: HRM encourages the people working in an organization, to work according to their potential and gives them suggestions that can help them to bring about improvement in it. The team communicates with the staff individually from time to time and provides all the necessary information regarding their performances and also defines their respective roles. This is beneficial as it enables them to form an outline of their anticipated goals in much clearer terms and thereby, helps them execute the goals with best possible efforts. Performance appraisals, when taken on a regular basis, motivate the employees. (iii). Maintaining Work Atmosphere: This is a vital aspect of HRM because the performance of an individual in an organization is largely driven by the work atmosphere or work culture that prevails at the workplace. A good working condition is one of the benefits that the employees can expect from an efficient human resource team. A safe, clean and healthy environment can bring out the best in an

employee. A friendly atmosphere gives the staff members' job satisfaction as well. (iv.) Managing Disputes: Conflicts are almost inevitable in an organization. In a School there are several issues on which disputes may arise between the employees and the employers. In such a scenario, it is the human resource department which acts as a consultant and mediator to sort out those issues in an effective manner. They first hear the grievances of the employees. Then they come up with suitable solutions to sort them out. In other words, they take timely action and prevent things from going out of hands. (v.) Developing Public Relations: The responsibility of establishing good public relations lies with the HRM to a great extent. They organize business meetings, seminars and various official gatherings on behalf of the school in order to build up relationships with other sectors of the economy. Any organization, without a proper setup for HRM is bound to suffer from serious problems while managing its regular activities. For this reason, today, companies must put a lot of effort and energy into setting up a strong and effective HRM. (www.humanresourceexcellence.com) Government and organization may build and equip all schools with the best science and technical equipment, provide all the basic educational materials, renovate and rehabilitate all old schools; provide library and other necessary facilities as well as the best qualified staff, yet the problem confronting educational administration would be half solved. Teachers who are the bedrock of any educational system need to be treated fairly well in terms of prompt settlement of their entitlements and enjoyment of other benefits enjoyed by other public servants. So until the human needs of the teachers are satisfied the desire of the government, parents and society for an improved educational system will be a hopeless dream and at best a nightmare; and investment in education will not be very beneficial to society in the final analysis.

Human resources management is the management of various activities designed to enhance the effectiveness of an organization's workforce in achieving organizational goals. To get work done, organizations need to attract people to apply for jobs and retain those who do their jobs well. After applicants have applied for a job offer, the process of selection occurs. Employers would over want to select employees who will be able and willing to learn new tasks and continually adapt to changing conditions. As job requirements change, existing employees must be able to develop new competencies, become proficient

in new jobs and even change their occupations. Training and development practices enable employees to develop themselves and remain employable (Jackson, S.E 2009). Performance must also be measured and employees must receive usable feedback so that they can correct performance deficiencies. In addition, employees work in exchange for compensation, monetary or otherwise. Employers on the other hand offer incentives and other forms of rewards to motivate employees to perform to their best. They must further provide a healthy and safe workplace and also give an ear to their employees' grievances. Human resources management encompasses a wide area and it can be said that good human resources management practices add value to a job and increase the job satisfaction. The review also covers literature on the dependent variables of this research conceptual framework. Notwithstanding the technological advances and new systems now available in the workplace the most important factor in the production of goods and services is the human factor. The other factors of production are only useful when they are operated by competent well motivated employees. Human resource management must change as the business environment in which it operates changes. Human resources management as defined by Armstrong (1999) is a strategic and coherent approach of the management of an organization's most valued assets, the people working there who individually and collectively contribute to the achievement of its goals. As defined by Storey (1995), human resource management is a distinctive approach to employment management which seeks to obtain competitive advantage through the strategic deployment of a highly committed and skilled workforce, using an array of cultural, structural and personal techniques. Human resources management practices and systems have been linked to organizational competitiveness, increased productivity, higher quality of work life and greater profitability (Cascio, 1992, Schuler and Jackson 1996). In a global economy, competitiveness means the ability to take the most advantageous position in a constantly changing market environment (Pfeffer, 1994). In order for this link to be accomplished between human resources management and organizational success, the role of human resources management must become strategic instead of operational, aligning the human resources function with the strategic needs of the organization (Pickles et al; 1999). Brewster (1995) reports that the integration of human resources management with business

strategy is rare even among the large organizations. Also, Down et al (1997) claim that many management teams have had difficulty transforming human resource management into a strategic function, leaving the human resources department in most companies focused on administrative and clerical tasks. Many organizations tend to focus on the administrative aspects of the HRM function, due to difficulties they face on the integration of HRM to organizational goals (Down et al; 1997). As a result, they ignore the long term perspective of HR planning and set their sights too low, ending up with HRM strategies that are too functional, too operational, too narrow and too generic (Walker, 1999). In the end, such strategies fail to energize their managers in making necessary changes to achieve competitiveness through people and often fade away or are replaced before they achieve any real impact. HRM strategies need to be integral to organizational strategies; they need to pay attention to multiple levels for strategy implementation, including organization, development, recruiting and staffing, rewards, performance and employee relations; they should provide for innovative ways to differentiate organizations in competitive markets and they must establish an achievable implementation of plan (Walker, 1999). The new strategic role for the HRM function entails two major aspects. First, the function should provide enough input into the organization's strategy about whether it has the necessary capabilities to implement it. Second, it has the responsibility to ensure that the HRM programs and practices are in place to effectively execute the strategy. The key functions of HRM differ from one organization to the other and from one country to another, but includes mainly the employment process, management of movement of employees in the organizations, employees motivations, reward management, performance management, personnel administration, training and development, exit management and employee welfare. Over the last 20 years there has been a growing interest in people management practices. In part this reflects the accumulating evidence that workers hold the key to enhanced organisational performance. Thus many of today's organizations are re-evaluating their human resource management (HR) practices in an attempt to tap workers' discretionary efforts and improve organisational performance (Park et al 2003). In many instances, the growing interest has been accompanied by a change in the nature and title of the personnel function, with former personnel managers now

referred to as human resource managers, and workers considered as 'valued employees' deserving respect and dignity from senior managers. Where such changes have occurred it is not uncommon to find human resource managers occupying strategic roles within organizations, alerting directors and other senior persons of the implications of change from a human capital perspective

The Innovative HR Practices

Many contemporary organizations use a range of HR practices that have become known as 'high performance', 'innovative' or 'high commitment' practices. In many instances the practices themselves are not new but the rationale for using them has changed. For instance, managers are now endeavoring to develop a committed and qualified workforce in a climate of trust and comradeship. This approach contrasts from the orthodox view in which employees were used dispassionately and rationally as any other capital resource. Furthermore, evidence suggests that when HR practices are used in conjunction with each other, the impact on performance will be greater than when used in isolation. In other words, organizations attempting to introduce individual HR practices will observe minimal if any change in performance, whereas those organisations successfully introducing a range of practices (generally referred to as 'bundles') will experience a more dramatic change in performance. Exactly what are the innovative practices? There are mixed views regarding the number and nature of such practices, but it is generally accepted that eight practices form the core. These are thought to represent those used by private sector managers who have successfully achieved competitive advantage through the workforce. However, it is unlikely that any one organization will utilize all these practices or even perform them equally well. Therefore, the list should be regarded, in the first instance at least, as a standard by which managers may monitor the level and extent of HR activity within their organisations (Murage, 2005). A preliminary study on Non Governmental Organizations in 2002 by William Gould identified the following inter-related human resource management practices as: employment security, rigorous selection process, incentive pay, effective communication systems or participation schemes, team forking, personal training and skill development programmes, symbolic egalitarianism and internal promotion. As highlighted earlier, it will be difficult to successfully implement one practice in isolation.

For instance, a rigorous selection process should ensure suitable candidates enter the organization. Thereafter, the organisation's personal training and development programme may then enhance the skills of these workers. As these capable individuals develop they are likely to qualify for more senior posts within the organisation, thus reinforcing policies of internal promotion. While the exact content and nature of these practices will vary between organisations, the underlying rationale for their adoption will be similar. Therefore, the following section will outline why and in what way these practices should be used.

Employment Security Today

It is unlikely that organizations can guarantee life-long employment to workers. Even in countries such as Japan where, until recently, such employment was the accepted norm, organizations have had to re-evaluate their position due to dramatic down turns in the world economy. However, while organizations may not be able to guarantee total employment security, the ways in which re-structuring or downsizing programmes are managed will signal to staff the extent to which managers value them. If workers are given the impression that they are dispensable, not valued or their jobs are insecure, it is highly probable that they will become de-motivated. This in turn may result in them feeling reluctant to exert themselves on behalf of the organization. If it is simply not possible for managers to guarantee extended periods of employment, they may need to consider ways to counteract feelings of insecurity felt by workers'. In the education sector, employment security has been quite guaranteed. Kenya teachers have continued to enjoy job security except for the case where a teacher is transferred unwillingly to a less attractive station. Such a teacher would feel not highly valued and even insecure. It is however the duty of the school head to create a conducive atmosphere in the school to make everybody feel that their contributions are valued (MOE & HRD, 2008)

Team working

Some commentators argue that organizations function better when employees are encouraged to work together as teams rather than on their own: Group forces are important not only in influencing the behaviour of individual work groups with regards to productivity, waste, absence and the like; they also affect the behaviour of entire organizations. It is argued that team working has a positive impact on

performance due to social interaction, peer pressure and work norms. In other words, assuming the group norms are favorable, group members will endeavour to maintain high working standards. Team working is also thought to provide workers with a forum through which they can learn 'through the grapevine'. These factors may lead to greater comradeship, peer support and team performance. Team effort, enhances school management and contributes towards employees' personal growth and development (Barasa J.M, 2004). In a team, each member is expected to work on his/her weaknesses and take criticism from colleagues positively. In a school setting, team effort thrives best where members relate to each other freely and openly

Training and Skill Development Programmes

Personal training and career development programmes have been used by many successful private sector companies as a way of ensuring they have a ready pool of labour within the organization. If undertaken in a coherent and integrated manner, the training programmes can help secure the commitment of workers who are able to visualize their current and future roles in the organization. It is also proposed that when organisations undergo programmes of change, they should up-date the skills and expertise of new and existing workers. Following such training programmes, managers will then need to review current working practices, systems and processes to ensure that newly trained employees are able to utilise their skills effectively. Failing to undertake such a review may result in the anticipated benefits of the training programmes being lost.

Following programmes of change many 'high performing' organisations strive to re-train or re-deploy staff, in order not to lose them. For instance, a manufacturing company underwent a significant upgrade of its working systems and introduced new IT systems. Rather than recruiting candidates from the external labour market, the company focused on developing the skills of the existing workforce. This signaled to the workforce that the company was serious about looking after them, and this in turn led to the company receiving positive benefits in terms of increased staff morale, numbers of employee suggestions, better qualified workers and lower absenteeism and labour turnover rates. Therefore, training and skill development programmes appear to have a range of positive effects on organisational performance, especially when integrated with the overall business objectives. School heads should

ensure that the staff has an opportunity to develop personal and professional skills (MOE & HRD, 2008). This may be by giving teachers a chance to attend appropriate In-service Education and Training.

METHODOLOGY

The survey research design was considered appropriate for this study. Survey is a process of collecting representative data from a higher population with the intention of generalizing the results to the population of interest (Mbua, 2003).

Survey is a quantitative research design. Quantitative researches designs are plans for carrying out research oriented towards quantification and are applied in order to describe current position conditions or to investigate relations. The main purpose of this study is to investigate what relationship exists between educational infrastructural inputs and wastage. A study like these needs a design with a plan and instrument that inquires the state and usage of infrastructural resources.

Area of the Study

This research was done in the south west region of Cameroon found in West Africa. It is a bilingual country that has ten regions. Southwest region capitals are Buea.

It's one of the two Anglophone (English speaking) regions of Cameroon. It's bordered to the east by the East region, to the North by the Center region to the west by the Gulf of Guinea (Part of the Atlantic Ocean) and to the South by countries of Equatorial Guinea, Gabon, and Congo. The South occupies 47,720 Km² of territory, making it the fourth largest region in the nation. The region is divided into six divisions: Lebialem, Manyu, Meme, Ndian, Kupe manugoba, fako division. These are in turn broken down into subdivisions. Presidentially appointed senior divisional officers govern each respectively.

About its geography, the soil is primarily ferrous. The south west is one of Cameroon's most economically areas due to its numerous plantations and the tourism generated by the beach. The area's economic strong hold, however it has a fair amount of industry; commercial agriculture is also important in the South west, the major cash crops being banana cocoa and

rubber. Plantain is the major crop grown; maize, groundnuts, cassava, yams and other foodstuffs are raised in more modest quantities. Cattle rearing and fishing are significant economic components, as well. Much of the population is made up of subsistence farmers.

Regarding education, the region was notable for having the first English-speaking University in Cameroon (The University of Buea). Other notable universities are catholic and Presbyterian universities. A good number of private higher institutions are found in this region, in addition to the public, lay private and confessional primary and secondary schools.

The south west region is considered as the best touristic region in the country to visit as the highest mountain in West Africa, Mount Cameroon is located in Fako division.

Population of the Study

A population refers to the complete collection of all the elements that are of interest in a particular investigation. It's especially the aggregate or totality of individuals, having one or more characteristics in common that are of interest to the researcher and where inferences are to be made in a particular study (Amin, 2005).

The target population (Which refers to the population in which the researcher ultimately wants to generalize the results, in this study constitute 94 secondary school principals in public, lay private and confessional schools in the Meme division. Secondary school principals are at the focal point of management of school inputs because they are head administrators.

There are in the position to manage greater percentage of school inputs in their school, especially those that are confidential use and may require the knowledge of all staff and students. Reduction of school repetition and school dropout in secondary schools also depend on how principals administer their schools principals were therefore chosen to make up the population of this study because they are in a better position to give information on how inputs are managed at all levels in their respective schools based on their position, knowledge and experience.

Table1: Distribution of secondary schools and their principals in the various divisions of the south west region of Cameroon.

Division	Type of school			Total	Total of principal
	Public	Lay private	Confessional		
Fako	39	43	18	100	100
Manyu	56	4	5	65	65
Kupe Mwanenguba	28	3	1	32	32
Ndian	31	2	1	34	34
Lebialem	32	3	2	37	37
Meme	56	6	32	94	94
Total	242	61	59	362	362

Source: Regional delegation of secondary education (2014/2015).List of secondary schools operating in the South west region

The accessible population or the population from which the researcher drew her sample consisted of one division in the south west region.

hand, and easy to reach by the researcher within a short time frame

Table 2: Accessible Population

Types of school	Number of schools	Total	Total number principal
Public	46	46	46
Lay private	22	22	22
Confessional	6	6	6
Total	74	74	74

Instrumentation

To carry out a quantitative study like this one, the researcher had to choose the most appropriate tool for data collection for effective measurement.

The instrument use to collect data in this study was a questionnaire on educational infrastructural inputs and wastage.

FINDINGS

This section of the study presents results based on the research question and hypotheses posed to address the Human Resources wastages in secondary schools in the Meme division of the South West Region of Cameroon.

Sample and Sampling Technique

In this study, Meme division was chosen by purposive sampling because repetition and drop out were more evident to the researcher in this division. 74 public, lay private and confessional schools and their respective principals in Meme were chosen using convenience sampling .This technique was chosen in other to select schools that are convenient close at

The scores from the response of the items that measure human resources were competed using the Chi -square test to test the hypothesis. The result of the analysis is presented as follow.

Table 3: Relationship between Qualified Teacher and School Repetition

Qualified teachers	Always		Sometime		Often		Never		Total	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
less than 20% Repetition rate	5	100	10	43.48	34	91.89	00	00	49	73.38
more than 20% repetition rate	100	00	13	56.52	3	8.10	00	00	16	24.62
Total	5	100	23	100	37	100	00	00	65	100

Table 4: Permitting to Calculated X²

0	Fe	lfe-fel	lf0-fel-0.5	(/f0-fe/-0.5) ²	(/f0-fe/-0.5) ²
5	3.77	1.23	0.73	0.53	0.14
00	1.23	1.23	0.73	0.53	0.43
F 10	17.33	7.33	3.63	46.64	2.69
13	5.66	7.34	6.84	46.64	2.69
34	27.89	6.11	5.61	31.47	1.12
3	9.11	6.11	5.61	31.47	3.45
00	00	00	-0,5	0.25	
00	00				
Total	64.79	29.35	25.45	57.67	16.08

X² calculated = 16.08

∞= 0.05 d11 =3

X² critical value =7.92

X² cal (18.08) >X² critical value (7.92)

Inference

This result of the analysis reveals that the calculated value (18.08) is greater than the critical value (7.92) at 0.5 level of significant with 3 degree of freedom. This led to the rejection of null hypothesis and the retaining of the alternative hypothesis, meaning that there is a significant

Table 5: Relationship between the Quantity of Teachers and School

Enough quantity of teachers	Always		Sometime		Often		Never		Total	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
less than 20% Repetition rate	7	100	10	52	35	75	00	00	49	75.38
more than 20% repetition rate	00	00	11	47.61	5	12.5	00	00	16	24.62
Total	7	100	21	100	40	100	00	00	65	100

Table 6: Permitting to Calculated X²

F0	Fe	(fe-fe)	lf0-fe/0.5	(/f0-fe/0.5) ²	(/f0 - fe/0.5) ² fe
7	5.28	1.72	1.22	1.48	0.05
00	1.72	1.72	1.22	1.48	0.87
10	15.83	5.33	5.33	28.40	2.84
11	5.17	5.83	5.33	28.40	5.49
35	30.15	4.85	4.35	18.92	0.62
5	9.85	4.35	4.35	18.92	3.78
00	00				
00	00				
Total	-68	24.8	21.8	97.6	13.65

X² calculated =13.65

∞=0.05 dell =3

X² critical value =7.92

Inference

The result of the analysis reveals that the calculated value (13.65) is greater than the critical value (7.92) at 0.5level of significance with 3 degree of freedom. This led to the rejection of null hypothesis and the retaining of the alternative hypothesis, meaning that there is a significant relationship between quantity of teachers and school repetition.

Table 7: Relationship between Teachers with Experience and School

Teachers with experience	Always		Sometime		Often		Never		Total	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
less than 20% Repetition rate	9	100	10	50	30	83.33	00	00	49	75.38
more than 20% repetition rate	00	00	10	50	6	16.67	00	00	16	24.64
Total	9	100	20	100	36	100	00	00	65	100

Table 8: Permitting To Calculated X^2

F0	Fe	(fe-fe)	lf0-fe/-0.5	(/f0-fe/-0.5) ²	$\frac{(/f0 - fe/-0.5)^2}{fe}$
9	6.78	2.22	1.72	2.96	0.43
00	2.22	2.22	1.72	2.96	1.33
10	15.08	5.8	5.3	28.09	1.86
10	4.92	5.08	4.58	20.98	5.71
30	27.14	5.08	4.58	20.98	0.77
6	8.86	2.36	2.86	5.57	0.08
00	00	00	-0.5	0.25	
00	00	00	-0.5	0.25	
Total	65	23.26	20.26	89.15	10.18

X^2 calculated = 10.18

X^2 critical value = 7.92

Inference

The result of the analysis reveals that the calculated value (10.18) is greater than the critical value (7.92) at 0.5 level of significance with 3 degree of freedom. This led to the rejection of null hypothesis and the retaining of the alternative hypothesis, meaning that the significance relationship between teachers with experience and school repetition.

Table 9: Relationship between Support Staff for Discipline and School

Staff for discipline	Always		Sometime		Often		Never		Total	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
less than 20% Repetition rate	10		7		32		00		49	73.38
more than 20% repetition rate	00		8		8		00		16	24.62
Total	10		15		40		00		65	100

Table 10: table permitting to calculate X^2

F0	Fe	(fe-fe)	lf0-fe/-0.5	(/f0-fe/0.5) ²	$\frac{(/f0 - fe/-0.5)^2}{fe}$
10	7.53	2.47	1.97	3.83	0.5
00	2.46	2.46	1.96	3.84	1.56
7	11.30	4.3	3.8	14.44	1.27
8	3.69	4.31	3.81	15.51	3.93
32	30.15	4.31	1.35	1.82	0.06
8	3.69	1.85	3.81	14.51	3.93
00	00				
00	00				
Total	58.82	19.7	16.7	54	11.27

X^2 calculated =11.27

$\infty=0.05$ d11 =3

X^2 critical value =7.92

X^2 cal (11.27) > X^2 critical value (7.92)

Inference

The result of the analysis reveals that the calculated value (11.27) is greater than the critical value at 0.5level of significance with 3 degree of freedom. This led to the rejection of null hypothesis and the retaining of the alternative hypothesis, meaning that there is a significance relationship between availability of support staff for discipline and school repetition.

Table 11: Relationship between Staff for Guidance and Counseling

Staff guidance counseling	Always		Sometime		Often		Never		Total	
	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%	Number	%
less than 20% Repetition rate	00	00	00	00	27	72.97	22	78.57	49	75.38
more than 20% repetition rate	00	00	00	00	10	27.03	6	21.43	16	24.62
Total	00	00	00	00	37	100	28	100	65	100

Table 12: Table Permitting To Calculated X^2

F0	Fe	(fe-fe)	lf0-fe/-0.5	(f0-fe/0.5) ²	$\frac{(f0 - fe / -0.5)^2}{fe}$
00	00	00	-0.5	0.23	
00	00	00	-0.5	0.23	
00	00	00	-0.5	0.23	
00	00	00	-0.5	0.23	
27	27.89	0.89	0.39	0.15	0.005
10	9.11	0.89	0.39	0.15	0.01
22	21.11	0.89	0.39	0.15	0.007
6	6.56	3.36	-0.44	1.6	0.04
Total	65	3.56	-0.44	1.6	0.04

X^2 calculated =0.042

$\infty=0.05$ d11 =3

X^2 critical value =7.92

X^2 cal (0.042) < X^2 critical value (7.92)

Inference

The result of the analysis reveals that the calculated value (0.042) is less than the critical value (7.99) at 0.5level of significance with 3 degree of freedom. This led to the rejection of alternative hypothesis, meaning that there is no significance relationship between staff for guidance and counseling and school repetition.

The Item intended to verify the relationship between qualified teachers and wastage.

Analyses revealed that 5 schools always have qualified teachers, 23 schools sometimes have

qualified teachers. It was also found that there is positive relationship between qualified teachers and wastage. As confirm by the result of hypothesis testing. Analyses shows that x^2 calculated (16.08) > x^2 calculated value (7.93). This means that when a school has qualified teachers, educational wastage can be reduce. When there is lack of qualified teachers, the rate of school repetition increases. This result agrees with the result of research Magnet (2007) that hold that student with certified teachers perform better than student with teachers who have no certification or emergency certificate. He also alerted that teachers, who have professional education training or

pedagogy, produce higher student's achievement than those who enter the profession and lack this background.

Item intended to verify the relationship between quantity and teachers at all the subjects and school repetition. Analyses revealed that 7 schools always have adequate quantity of teachers in all the subjects 21 schools, sometimes have adequate quality in all the subjects and 40 schools often have adequate quantity of teachers in all the subjects. It was also found that there is a positive relationship between enough quantity of teachers in all subjects and school repetition. As confirm by the result of table above shows that χ^2 calculated (13.69) > χ^2 critical value (7.92). This means that quantity of teachers in the entire subject can reduce the rate of repetition.

Item intended to verify the relationship between teachers with experience and school repetition. Analyses revealed that 9 schools always have teachers with experience, 20 schools sometimes have teachers with experience, 36 schools often have teachers with experience. It was also found that there is positive relationship between teachers experience and school repetition. As confined by the result above .It shows that χ^2 calculated (10.18)> χ^2 critical (7.92) value. This means that schools which have teachers with experience can have low rate of repetition, while schools which have teachers without experience can have high rate of school repetition. This result agree with magnet (2007) finding, who hold that there is a negative effect when a high proportion of inexperienced teachers are present in school, in terms of higher dropout rate and lower students achievement scores.

Item intended to verify the relationship between support staff for discipline and school repetition.

Analyses shows that, 10 schools always have support staff for discipline,15 schools sometimes have support staff for discipline, 40 schools often have support staff for discipline. It was found that there is a positive relationship between availability of support staff for discipline and school repetition. As confirmed by the result of table above. It reveals that χ^2 calculated (11.27) > χ^2 critical value (7.92).

This means that the availability of support staff for discipline can reduce the rate of school repetition.

Item intended to verify the relationship between availability of guidance and counseling and school repetition. Table above reveals that 71 schools often have staff for guidance and counseling. It was also found that there is no positive relationship between availability of staff for guidance and counseling and school repetition. As confined by the result of table 71. It shows χ^2 calculated (0.042) < χ^2 critical value (7.92) this mean that the availability of staff for guidance and counseling does not influence the rate of repetition in school.

Results from this study and those of other researches show that when human resources of standards are available in school, there will be low rate of educational wastage. On the other hand, if these resources are neglected or left out completely, there will be high rate of school wastages. It also reveals that human is still lacking in a higher percentage in schools.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, it should be note that lack of schools inputs is a reality that crosses all educational system in the world, especially developing countries. The availability of adequate school inputs can initiate productive change in school system by increasing student achievement. The resultant consequence of lack of this school inputs will inevitably increase the rate of school wastage. It has been demonstrated in this study and other related studies that availability of computers, teaching aids, text books for teachers and students, supply for teachers, library, qualified teachers, adequate quantity of teachers in school, teachers with experience, support staff for discipline can contribute to reduce the rate of educational wastages. It was also demonstrated that schools with high rate of repetition had high rate of drop out. It is important to emphasis the cleaver word of Bonseroning (2013) as cited in Bombay (2014):"Education production involves teachers, students and a number of other actors. The effects of these actors and their implicated interaction are the determinant of the student achievement".

It should be understood that the supply of adequate educational input in schools is successfully in resolving the problem of school wastage. also worth noting is the fact that other attributes like longevity in service, gender, school location which were extraneous variables in this study can influence

educational wastage. Mbua (2003) pointed that a close analysis of the survival rate shows that boys persist in school is slightly higher than girls. However, the more important disparity between boys and girls is evidence in the overall enrollment figure for the less developed region, three quarters of 8 million school entrance age children who did not enter school in 1994 -1995 were students from rural areas (Mbua,2003). He demonstrated that rural schools often have higher dropout rate than urban schools.

Principals with academic qualification may tend to possess better managerial skills of educational inputs than principal with lower academic qualification as shown by Egboke & ai, (2012) as cited in Bornbey, (2014) who founded that principal did not possess the managerial skills for effective management of secondary school inputs because most of them had low academic qualification. The post of principals has been allocated to them because of longevity in service as teacher.

In order to manage this problem of schools wastage, school inputs should be equally distributed to all the schools. Also worth noting is the fact that other attribute like longevity in service, gender, school location which were extraneous variables in this study can influence the school wastage. Research has shown that Skills are well mastered with experience and UNESCO statistic (2005) show that girls drop out from school more than boys. Students in rural area drop out from school more than students in urban area.

RECOMMENDATION

Base on the finding of this study, the following are recommendations that will improve on the reduction of educational wastage and eventually improve educational achievement.

- Policy makers should ensure that decision about whether a child repeat is based on objective, national criteria that are applied equitably across schools and regions.
- A clear communication strategy needs to be developed so that all stakeholders are aware of the new policy, understand why promotion is replacing repetition as the first choice solution to children who are struggling, and are supported in the "how to" of implementing it at school and community level.

- The state should ensure the quality and relevance of education and teaching
- The state should make the transition from repetition to automatic promotion The teacher should provide out of class and non mainstreamed support through special need provision and home work
- Formal identification of an individual special learning needs and the allocation of resources for that individual need from government in addition to the school normal funding.
- The state should provide schools with satisfactory facilities and conditions for students and teachers.
- The government should give annual subvention or grant to enable private schools subsidise the payment of teachers salaries and other related course.
- The teacher should provide out of school non mainstream support through special need provision and homework.

Suggestion for Further Research

This same study can be carried out in other regions of Cameroon on the management of educational input by school authorities in Cameroon secondary schools.

Others relevant studies can be conducted on:

- The effect of school location on wastage in secondary schools in all the regions.
- The relationship between type of schools and wastage in secondary school.
- The relationship between gender education and wastage in secondary school.

Limitation of the Study

The result of this study may have been affected negatively because of the following constraints:

- All the questionnaires administered were not returned. The information on the questionnaire that was not returned would have added more value to this, study.
- .On the returned questionnaires, there were certain items that were not answered, resulting to missing values for that items. This factor is also a limiting factor. It result in a minus of some information that would have added value to this study.
- .A few principals especially in Mbonge sub division did not respond correctly to the questionnaires. They assigned another school administrator to respond on their behalf. This action may have biased the data obtained.

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